

UK National Data Library: Distributed Architecture for Research

National Data Library

Distributed architecture for research

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Introduction

The data landscape for research and the public sector in the UK today is fragmented into thousands of disconnected databases. Our vision is to establish a National Data Library (NDL) using a distributed architecture that drives growth and improves public services.

Data is plentiful, but the UK lacks data orchestration and governance. The situation is reminiscent of telecommunications before standardised internet protocols, many local implementations which allowed information to flow within local domains, like banks or government but without interoperability. In its simplest form, this paper wants to do for research what TCP-IP did for the internet - create a common data interchange protocol and technical architecture. We make three fundamental decisions: the open standard for how data is stored, the mechanisms for data to be shared, and the governance required to connect trusted parties to these data.

Our technical white paper will outline an operational architecture to ensure ease of access and interoperability while maintaining public trust. By leveraging secure cloud collaboration, template-driven infrastructure architectures, and proven, scalable technologies, we propose a blueprint for an economically viable ecosystem that shares valuable data applications and insights.

This paper focuses on user needs, benefits realisation, technical architecture, and sustainable management of the NDL. Together, these can make the UK the global leader in research data infrastructure.

Vision

Our approach offers a step change in accessibility, security, engagement and breadth of research. It will move us away from discrete silos of data that give a partial population view in a single modality to a world of 'on-demand' integrated data across multiple providers for a given project, with standardised workflows and approaches to citizen engagement and information governance.

We cannot solve all the issues with interoperable digital systems across the UK public sector. However, we cannot solely focus on de-identified population science using Section 251 approvals. We must cater for fundamental discovery and translational science, which is driven by identifiable cohorts of individuals – new drugs and AI require that new datasets be explored before being codified. An NDL cannot limit itself to pseudonymised tabular data but must also contend with multiple data modalities (images, EHRs, genomes, sensor data) and work with high-performance on-premises computing clusters, including national supercomputing investments like AIRR¹.

We are guided by nine principles that increase public trust, reproducibility, and sustainability while decreasing complexity, reducing costs and mitigating risk.

¹ Christley, S. et al., 'The ADC API: A Web API for the Programmatic Query of the AIRR Data Commons', *Frontiers in Big Data*, 3 (2020).

Principles

1. Services are customer-driven, not centrally determined.
2. We prefer analytical code to be open-sourced rather than reinvented.
3. We should minimise data duplication wherever possible.
4. Personal data should remain as close to the source as possible to provide security and ease of privacy management.
5. Code moves to the data rather than moving data.
6. Personal identifiers should be the last resort when linking datasets.
7. Simple access to data is essential, as friction and complexity reduce usage and value.
8. We trust domain experts to develop their own data assets
9. Design must be iterative and responsive to changing needs.

Our technical vision builds on the [LATTICE architecture](#) the Francis Crick Institute developed. Unlike a traditional library where books holding information are stored in one physical location we propose a consolidated but distributed fabric of data controllers and research-performing organisations working in an open data format, connected via a common data catalogue, registry framework and citizen consent using best practice security and technical standards. The value of a data fabric approach is that it allows for true federation - central oversight, record-keeping, common tools and technology access, and local information governance and curation.

Figure 1. The LATTICE architecture, supporting the national ecosystem

1. **Data controllers** own and curate their data, which is stored on their preferred cloud provider.
2. **Data nodes** define data management standards for their domain, covering quality, interoperability, standards, security, tagging and data engineering.
3. **Citizens, researchers and data controllers** access the governance process management layer to both onboard new datasets and make requests to access data. Each controller defines their information governance approval workflow. It also controls the onboarding and offboarding of datasets and approved organisations and users, writing all of these to registry tables.
4. **Trusted Research Environments** are created using a standard ‘infrastructure as code’ template following the IG sign-off of a research project. The requested sub-set of the data is shared directly into secure workspaces using the Data Fabric Orchestration layer. This both automates the process to minimise administrative overhead and ensures every share is recorded in a registry and linked to the people, project and approval for total transparency and auditability.
5. **Products** can be created by both individuals and organisations to provide value across the ecosystem. For example, a ‘personal’ view can be created to show citizens how their data is being used, in what studies and under what basis of consent – section 251 or explicit cohort consent etc. – using information from the data catalogue and registries. Equally, new data services ‘APIs’ could be created to power new digital services within the public sector, such as a unified health record.
6. **A marketplace** of data assets and applications that allows for multiple licence models to be applied to the data, with different incentive structures possible, allowing for citizens, researchers and commercial organisations to share their outputs
7. **The ecosystem** consumes products and ultimately feeds new data back into the library.

In developing the vision for the NDL, we are focusing on meeting the needs of citizens, researchers and organisations to access and innovate on public data, securely link data across trusted research environments (TREs) and standardise the governance required to deliver world-class research. This will help to improve public services and grow the UK economy. Our primary objective is to create a strong ecosystem that is self-sustaining. When compromises between user needs must be made, they should be done in service of the ecosystem, not the individual research organisation.

We are proposing LATTICE as an overarching technical architecture and highlighting a series of configurations within this architecture that enable these benefits. Developing a national

infrastructure will be technically challenging, and we believe it is not feasible or preferable to develop each component internally. So, this architecture relies heavily on integrating and configuring existing technologies.

The realisation of this ambitious project will require a dedicated organisation to develop the technology architecture and to manage and engage the vast ecosystem effectively. We see parallels with existing critical national infrastructure organisations, such as Network Rail and Openreach, with specialist teams that oversee and ensure the standards of data storage, sharing and connectivity required for this to succeed.

Governance

To support the development of the NDL, we also recommend five cross-cutting panels, staffed with high-calibre individuals with significant domain expertise, to provide oversight, assurance and governance:

1. Technical advisory panel – to discuss technical solutions, verify approaches, spread knowledge and build consensus.
2. Social contract panel – to capture the views of patients and the public on how to best allow them agency in the use of their data, determine usable and accessible solutions and strengthen the social contract around using their data for research.
3. Information governance advisory panel – to discuss the impacts on existing practice and proposed mitigations.
4. Research advisory panel – to ensure that the solutions proposed fit the needs of cutting-edge clinical research, and to offer use cases and guidance to progress the development roadmap.
5. All-party parliamentary group - to ensure that members of the House of Commons and House of Lords have the opportunity to discuss and debate the merits of the National Data Library and how it benefits citizens, public sector services and economic growth.

Context

Despite the significant and valuable effort in this space, the lack of a centralised strategy, policy and funding for architecting and sharing data has meant that there are now 291 million possible ways of interrogating primary care health data for 55 million people². There is a huge amount of duplication and no mechanism of sharing data consistently across TREs without physically copying data. There has been progress on standardising safety. All NDL infrastructure should be designed in accordance with the Five Safes framework: safe data, safe projects, safe people, safe settings and safe outputs.³

Investment in ‘federation’ so far has focused predominantly on academic pilot projects, which have largely acted as software demonstration exercises. They offer no clear pathway to national critical infrastructure scale or the ‘any to any’ connectivity needed to make a national data federation operate.

The DARE UK program has completed its first phase, and we will be drawing heavily from some of its proof of concepts to support this NDL architecture. In particular, we will be drawing heavily from the “Virtual” TRE technical annex to create on-demand TREs led by the Francis Crick Institute⁴.

Progress has already been made in creating citizen registries, a privacy-preserving federation, data discovery, public data access, and accreditation.

Citizen registries: NHS England created a Personal Demographic service⁵ to cover the entire population of England.

Privacy-preserving federation: OpenSafely has demonstrated a federated approach to health data research, where code moves to data rather than data to code, enabling the analysis of 57 million patients.

² Zhang, J., Morley, J., Gallifant, J., Oddy, C., Teo, J. T., Ashrafian, H., et al. (2023). Mapping and evaluating national data flows: transparency, privacy, and guiding infrastructural transformation. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 1(7), e342-e351. Retrieved from

[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/article/PIIS2589-7500\(23\)00157-7/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/article/PIIS2589-7500(23)00157-7/fulltext)

³ UK Data Service. (2024). What is the Five Safes Framework? [UK Data Service].

<https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/>

⁴ Jena-Smol, A., Wileman, T., & Rosa, N. (2022). ‘Virtual’ TREs Service Design. Retrieved from

<https://dareuk.org.uk/>

⁵ NHS England. (2024). Personal Demographics Service. [NHS England]. Retrieved from

<https://digital.nhs.uk/services/personal-demographics-service>

Data discovery: The HDRUK Health Data Research Gateway⁶ provides access to metadata, access routes, publications and the ability to federate basic cohort analysis across a network of secure data environments

Public data access: Fingertips⁷, originally developed with Public Health England, is an interface and API that provides access to a range of health statistics across the UK.

Accreditation Under the Digital Economy Act 2017, the UK Statistics Authority has accredited 12 environments that can link, match, process and de-identify data. The Office of National Statistics has developed a research accreditation service⁸ with nearly 6,000 researchers currently accredited.

Technical Architecture

We build on the [LATTICE architecture](#), a cloud-agnostic data management and analytics platform that complements existing TREs. It provides accredited researchers with access to citizen data that is legally approved for processing. The first 'real' version of the architecture, developed by the Francis Crick Institute for use in its research programmes, will make use of a core technology set of:

- Okta for Identity and Access Management
- ServiceNow for Governance Process Management
- Snowflake as the Data Fabric
- AWS, Azure and GCP as the Storage
- Ansible workflows to deliver the Orchestration Layer

The diagrams in the rest of this section show how the same conceptual architecture can be delivered using different technologies to perform key functions. As the NDL must in time, accommodate and integrate with as wide a set of pre-existing TRE investments as possible, we foresee the Orchestration Layer being continuously developed to integrate these.

This provides an automated methodology for safe infrastructures that can be spun up on demand. We codify governance through a CI/CD approach, creating the required resources, furnishing those resources with containerised applications for development, and supporting the management of role-based access through registries.

⁶ Health Data Research UK. (2024). The Health Data Research Gateway. Retrieved from <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/research/research-data-infrastructure/the-gateway/>

⁷ Office for Health Improvement and Disparities. (2024). Fingertips Public Health Profiles. Retrieved from <https://fingertips.phe.org.uk/>

⁸ Office for National Statistics. (2024). Accessing secure research data as an accredited researcher. Retrieved from <https://www.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/whatwedo/statistics/requestingstatistics/approvedresearcherscheme>

This technology is cloud agnostic (deployable across Azure, AWS, GCP), global in coverage, and data type (binary files or coded data). Providing all the tools needed to build a modern data science environment: storage, elastic compute and security.

It also offers unique capabilities that solve the complexities of secure collaboration. We articulate the capability for a data query or code to be passed to the data without the data leaving the infrastructural control of its owner, allowing analysis without copying datasets. This will enable researchers to work with data as if they had a physical local copy, including combining it with other datasets, without the data controller losing control of the data to a third party. This essential facility resolves the core paradox of maximal sharing and flexibility with maximal control.

Below, we illustrate three instantiations based on this architecture: anonymous data for population-level analysis and reporting, sensitive data that is routinely collected, and research-generated data for consented cohorts.

1. An [automated orchestration of on-demand, cloud-agnostic federated TREs](#) suitable for:
 - a. Accredited researchers linking data across TREs for consented cohorts
 - b. Research organisations developing novel research proposals
2. A [publicly available open source data portal and marketplace](#) suitable for:
 - a. Non-technical citizens looking for answers from public data
 - b. Technical citizens developing an application using public data
 - c. Commercial organisations developing data products and applications
3. [Data clean rooms](#) for privacy-preserving standardised population federated analysis, suitable for:
 - a. Accredited researchers conducting whole-population research
 - b. Civil servants monitoring and modelling public sector performance

These configurations provide a [cloud- and vendor-agnostic approach](#) to the NDL architecture that is standardised, modular, scalable, open and secure. We anticipate the need for six operational enablers for this to succeed.

1. A [citizen consent registry](#) based on [atomic consent actions](#)
2. A [research accreditation service and identity management](#)
3. [Privacy-enhancing technology for universal citizen de-identification](#) and linkage
4. [Standardised collaboration agreements](#)
5. [National Data Library reproducible analytical pipelines](#)
6. [Registry infrastructure](#) to validate researcher, institutional and project identity

Automated orchestration of on-demand cloud-agnostic federated TREs

Figure 2. Example on demand federated TRE

1. **Governance process management and orchestration** using a standardised collaboration agreement based on a registry of organisations, projects and researchers. Once approved, a copy of the GitHub project template is created and configured to create the resources deployed through a CI/CD pipeline. Infrastructure as code manages the resources required for the environment, ensuring the appropriate resources for storage, compute, networking and security exist within the instantiation. Ansible is used to manage the necessary containerised applications. This allows the Polaris catalogue, query layer and relevant development applications to use the resources. Containers for this project are pre-approved and accessed through a private docker registry
2. **The deidentification service** creates research-ready tables that can be stored within the data node in the Iceberg format.
3. **Supporting multiple storage archetypes**. Tables managed in a separate cloud can be connected via private links and private service connections that cause them to act as if they were within the same cloud. On-premises datasets will require temporary cloud

storage for data to be shared within the NDJ. Nodes that share the same cloud infrastructure will take advantage of the regional sharing. There will still be cases where data copying is unavoidable, such as where new lab data, unstructured data or binary file types will be transferred where double-wrapped encryption protocol is used.

4. **The data catalogue** manages nodes as catalogues, limiting query engines to read-only access and establishing fine-grained control over which services and roles can access tables through the governance-as-code approach.
5. **Automated deployment** of applications is required for analysis and code development alongside logging, auditing, and disclosure control.
6. **Citizens control** what is legally permissible through linking to the atomic actions and rights defined by each consented citizen.
7. **Accredited researchers** access the infrastructure through secure IAM services.
8. **Final egress outputs** are manually validated by the governance and oversight groups for the project.

Open source data portal and marketplace

This section shows how the same conceptual architecture can be delivered using open-source technologies. It presents the use case of an 'open data' portal that provides access to all UK government statistics and anonymous data assets to technical and non-technical citizens and the capability to share the results of that analysis through marketplaces of code and applications.

Historically, open data releases within the UK have been developed as monthly published statistics, often stored as multi-sheet Excel files, which change format and structure over time. This makes developing analysis and models on top of datasets challenging, requiring manual changes and no guarantee downstream pipelines will work month to month. It is possible to move from an Excel-based data file approach to a common open data format, encouraging the creation of larger, stable, backwards compatible and self-defining data tables.

Figure 3. Open source data portal and marketplace

- 1. Development of Catalogs in each data node containing anonymous data.** Open-source Apache Iceberg was created to address the challenges of managing data lakes spread over distributed storage, which enables data consistency and improves query performance as datasets grow and schema evolve. This allows each public sector data controller to securely manage what data is shared and link to the data catalogue without transferring data across to a centralised resource in a cost-effective, performant pattern.
- 2. Integration with a rest catalogue to manage access to anonymous data.** Apache Polaris is an interoperable open-source catalogue for Iceberg tables that allows role-based access control at the data catalogue level alongside short-lived credentials to query engines, protecting tables, namespaces, and views from improper access, integrating with multiple cloud storage providers.
- 3. Query engines and compute providers to provide highly performant querying of Iceberg tables.** These work at the location where the data is stored, preventing the data from being unnecessarily duplicated and moved from the data node to the central resource.

4. **Human-readable catalogue and Shared codebases.** A human-readable catalogue of data assets allows data to be discovered and accessed across research environments, government departments, and arms-length bodies. The catalogue is available to all stakeholders, with access to the public data through a browser-based interface and linking to the commercially available marketplaces for data assets. Open APIs are available for technical users, and the analytical data pipelines using these should be open source by default, increasing reproducibility and reducing time to insight.
5. **AI integration.** A NDL should take every technological advantage to provide non-technical citizens with insight from publicly available data. The NDL will require a natural language for SQL services that utilise open-source LLM models such as Mistral Large to return data that answers citizen queries.
6. **Linking to existing commercial data marketplaces,** the NDL can leverage tried and tested infrastructure to manage external data products and applications.

Data clean rooms for standardised population federated analysis

UK public services routinely collect data at the citizen level. These consistent datasets are candidates for local linkage and storage and, when combined with a common data model, can be used as an eyes-off architecture for population-level federated analysis. This approach follows the concepts developed and proven through the OpenSafely program and the TRE-FX pilot⁹ enabling the improvement of public services without sharing data beyond the local setting.

In this paradigm, code is developed in sandbox environments before being approved and federated out to the local nodes, approved for egress, and outputted as anonymous data available to share. This anonymity prevents any data from being processed outside its legal borders and expands the number of researchers and analysts who can use it.

Public sector services are consistent at the local level, and schemas used to share data nationally already exist within the NHS, councils, transport, and policing. Rather than mandating national data lakes that ingest all this data into a central repository, there is the option to create local integrated services that will minimise the transport of data and connect it locally rather than nationally.

Developing a common data model, query approach, and corresponding synthetic data allows this architecture to flow code to data rather than data to code. In doing so, we create a “data clean room,” and, with the appropriate disclosure controls, ensure that only anonymous data is ever shared with the researcher.

⁹ TRE-FX: Delivering a federated network of trusted research environments to enable safe data analytics. (2024). Retrieved from <https://trefx.uk/>

Figure 4. Data clean rooms for standardised population federated analysis

1. Projects that are suitable for federated analysis are approved.
2. An automated data clean room is spun up on demand (as defined above).
3. Synthetic data that conforms to the common data model of the local integrated TRE and stored in the Iceberg format allows researchers to develop the analysis code required.
4. Once this analytical code has been appropriately tested a pull request is made. The NDL team reviews the pull request, which, if approved, moves to the submission and orchestration layer. The orchestration layer ensures the transfer of the code to the local TREs required for the analysis.
5. Each of these TREs hosts a containerised set of features that enables the authentication of incoming jobs, manages the resources needed for these jobs and executes code against the Polaris catalogue across the linked datasets. The TRE has disclosure control through manual approval by TRE administrators.
6. The NDL team manages the final disclosure control before the outputs are shared with researchers and the code is made available for public inspection.

Operational architectures

Citizen privacy and citizen consent management

Where data is confidential, personal, or identifiable, there must be a legal basis for processing this data for one of the following purposes: vital interests, public task, legal obligation, contract, legitimate interest, or consent. Today, many of the secure healthcare data environments are using section 251 to gain specific and limited permission for processing confidential special category (health) data for research. This enables a standardised federation of data across these data nodes but, depending on the specifics of the confidentiality advisory group application, prevents linking this data outside of this secure data environment and, therefore, with the infrastructure of a NDL.

Similar legislative challenges exist for sharing data across government departments, for example, between the Department of Work and Pensions and His Majesty's Revenue and Customs, despite there often being a legal basis for processing and linking this data. Vital interests, public tasks, and legitimate interests cover only a few of the possible research uses that a NDL can support. The simplest solution to ensuring citizen privacy is respected is to codify and manage consent and rights throughout the data collection and processing lifecycle.

Consent is a broad term, and in this paper, we build upon prior work by the Crick Institute to propose a citizen consent registry¹⁰ based on a set of [atomic actions](#) and [rights](#). These should form the basis of the software approach to managing citizen consent required for a fully functioning NDL. This concept is not necessarily novel, with several other initiatives having attempted something similar in the past. However, it is unique in integrating directly with trusted research infrastructure and major secure data environments and being research agnostic.

As with the Project-TRE platform, we propose creating something generic and nationally scalable. The patient portal requirements will evolve through the societal engagement work but will start with providing visibility of the consents and projects the patient has engaged with.

¹⁰ Barnsley, P., & Fleming, J. (2023). Consent and Rights within human healthcare IT solutions for lawful basis processing. Retrieved from https://crick.figshare.com/articles/report/Consent_and_Rights_within_human_healthcare_IT_solutions_for_lawful_basis_processing/23587131?file=41378052

Research Accreditation service and identity management

We also propose an approval process for verifying, maintaining and blacklisting researchers wishing to access sensitive data. This can build on the existing work by the ONS Secure Research Service¹¹ ensuring statistical disclosure is prevented but adding in the necessary training required to share analytical processing steps using version control systems such as Git to configure their research environments. A blacklist for researchers who jeopardise the trust placed in the NDL will act as a deterrent and prevent researchers from bouncing between TREs. Identity management should be managed by a dedicated provider. Okta is currently being used by The Crick and many other TREs for this purpose, which integrates the Okta SAML application and necessary groups to add the users required for access.

National Data Library reproducible analytical pipelines

The amount of rework and reprocessing of datasets across the research and public sector landscape is enormous. In most TREs, each project is considered entirely separate, and the data engineering, business logic, and feature engineering used in modelling are repeated in slightly different ways. Ensuring the analytical code used as part of any project is published will dramatically reduce the time for new projects to get started and create a community of analysts, statisticians, economists and data scientists that can develop templates for specific datasets, approaches and use cases. The examples of Kaggle Notebooks and Google Colab Notebooks demonstrate the power of a community gradually building on top of previous work, while the hundreds of different methods across the government to execute similar analytical tasks demonstrate why the lack of shared analytical code is hampering productivity.

Privacy-enhancing technology for universal citizen de-identification and linkage

A privacy-enhancing technology service that provides a consistent mapping of personally identifiable data to a shared research record should be used across TREs. This identity-as-a-service function will prevent the multiple personal keys being used in today's linkage approaches and provide one organisation with the responsibility of managing the persistent edge cases and errors that plague linkage attempts across the research landscape. This service will enable effective linkage across settings based on individuals, households and organisations by creating a map of keys to link identifiers for research:

¹¹ Office for National Statistics. (2024). Accessing secure research data as an accredited researcher. Retrieved from <https://www.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/whatwedo/statistics/requestingstatistics/approvedresearcherscheme>

Standardised collaboration agreements

Automating the components of the contractual agreements between research organisations could be the innovation that most dramatically accelerates research. Each project has to go through the same processes, but the lack of standardisation has meant that the sequence and structure of the requests often result in a ping-pong of documents between parties. This is outlined in the DARE UK - “Virtual TREs” summary report¹², which outlines the development of a software platform that automatically documents the necessary steps in the workflow below:

Figure 5 Collaboration workflow diagram

This includes ethical approvals, intellectual property agreements, data sharing agreements, and budget information using a consistent and templated approach.

Trusted Research Registry Infrastructure

The NDLE will partner with existing projects such as the HDR UK Researcher Registry¹³ and the ONS Safe Researcher program¹⁴. Still, where a registry is missing, work will propose a design and solution for the missing components. The full set of registries will integrate and scale to

¹² Jena-Smol, A., Wileman, T., & Rosa, N. (2022). ‘Virtual’ TREs Service Design. Retrieved from <https://dareuk.org.uk/>

¹³ Health Data Research UK. (2024). Data Use Registers. Retrieved from <https://www.hdr.uk.ac.uk/access-to-health-data/data-use-registers/>

¹⁴ Office for National Statistics. (2024). Become an accredited researcher. Retrieved from <https://www.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/whatwedo/statistics/requestingstatistics/secureresearchservice/becomeanaccred>

cover the entire UK research and public services landscape. As needed, the project will convene a UK-wide community discussion of these new registry designs. This will require the preparation of APIs to enable new registry services to be created, exploiting the existing research evaluation processes used by UKRI¹⁵ where every grant award is tracked, along with the awardees and their affiliations. This activity will turn those databases into web services with APIs, which can be called by any information governance workflow for any SDE, TRE, or other purpose. This will eliminate the need to start due diligence on every information governance request from scratch, moving towards a 'data passport' approach. This will demonstrate the integration of these registries into the orchestration and identification processes of the technical architecture outlined above.

Economics of a National Data Library

Government organisations often face significant challenges in developing and maintaining large-scale data infrastructure. This typically involves substantial upfront costs and ongoing management expenses. While collaborative models, such as those used in life science missions, can alleviate some of these burdens, a more comprehensive commercial approach is necessary to optimise the value and sustainability of a National Data Library.

We expect the National Data Library provision to include several costs:

- Set-up costs for the initial configuration of the technology and associated governance.
- Management costs to ensure the library is relevant, ingests new data, meets requirements and remains easy to use.
- Ongoing usage cost for egress and hosting of additional data sets.
- Development of user-focused applications to allow natural language interaction with the data set, including model improvement.

A commercial model could involve charging fees for data extraction based on factors like data volume and usage. This approach would incentivise data providers to maintain high-quality, user-friendly data formats and allow users to choose the most suitable data extraction methods. A commercial model can drive significant benefits for the public, research and private sectors by streamlining data access and fostering innovation.

There is also a question of whether the data should be provided for free or at a fee. The Government currently has a variety of models for this, such as the NHS SDE programme and the ONS data acquisition policy. This will need to be considered over time to ensure consistency

¹⁵ UK Research and Innovation. (2022). UKRI Strategy 2022-2027: Transforming tomorrow together [Section 2.4: Towards 2.4%: Creating a global science superpower; UKRI Evaluation Strategy]. Retrieved from <https://www.ukri.org/publications/uk-research-and-innovation-evaluation-strategy/ukri-evaluation-strategy/>

in the library in a way that allows for simplicity while also recognising local compensation routes. Having this designed effectively also incentivises the provision of high-quality data. In addition, tiered pricing structures and potential subsidies for specific user groups must be considered to ensure equitable access and affordability. A robust governance framework should also be established to oversee data quality, security and ethical considerations.

We recommend exploring a commercial model where a fee is paid at the time of data sharing based on the data's assigned value and any egress cost. The provider responsible for delivering the data egress should cover this cost, as well as any additional commercial fee. This approach allows the data user to choose how to access the data and ensures that the commercial entity reimburses the Government annually for the use of the data. Consequently, the Government would not need to enter into multiple contracts.

This model resembles the provision of frameworks, where the framework provider covers the framework fee and setup costs. The licensing for this provision would require these organisations to pay a fee back to the Government. Fees would be set by the data owners, and over time, any costs would be determined by market conditions. Additionally, this structure would encourage data providers to make data available in user-friendly, up-to-date formats. It also allows users to select their data egress provider based on their current data warehousing tools.

- Quantify benefits, including the impact on increased data quality, faster innovation and cost savings for the Government and users.
- Ensure there is a design that can prioritise data sovereignty and security. What safeguards can be put in place to incentivise commercialisation?
- Consider a hybrid model that combines elements of public and private sector involvement. This could involve partnerships with commercial entities to provide specific services, such as data curation or analysis.

Conclusion

As proposed in this paper, the UK National Data Library represents a significant advancement in using data to promote innovation, enhance public services, and support scientific research. By establishing a robust, secure, and interoperable infrastructure, we can unlock the potential of data across the UK data landscape

This vision is grounded in a commitment to data privacy, security, and ethical considerations. The LATTICE architecture offers a flexible and scalable framework that allows for the secure sharing and analysis of sensitive data while enabling effective collaboration among researchers and organisations using modular components to avoid vendor or cloud lock-in.

By implementing the suggested operational and technical strategies, the UK can position itself as the global leader in data-driven innovation, fostering a thriving data ecosystem that benefits society.

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